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CHALLENGES IN MEASURING FLAME CHARACTERISTICS UNDER HYDROGEN-OXYFUEL CONDITIONS

INTERNATIONAL FLAME RESEARCH FOUNDATION

**TOTeM 52 – Oxy-fuel combustion and
CCUS**
Essen, Germany

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Introduction - Goals in the industry

[1]

Introduction

Scale up

[2]

Burner from the glass melting furnace

- Nozzle-mixing oxygen burner with a power level up to 50 kW
- Fuel supply via internal burner nozzle
- Enclosing oxygen supply through annular gap with swirl channels

Modular combustion channel

- 4 interchangeable segments (max. wall temperature 1600°C)
- Detection of the entire flame length through movable burner block
- Gas mixing section consisting of the following components: Natural gas, H₂, N₂, CO₂, O₂, air

TC ... Thermocouple
 OA ... Optical access
 EG ... Exhaust gas

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Endress+Hauser multi-analysis system

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OH-PLIF Setup

- **Nd:YAG laser** (Quantel, Q-Smart 850, 850 mJ/pulse) generates the **fundamental laser beam of 1064 nm**
- Second Harmonic Generator doubled the frequency to the laser beam to 532 nm
- **Nd:YAG laser pumps the dye laser** (Sirah Lasertechnik GmbH, Cobra Strech) at a repetition rate of 10 Hz
- Dye laser operates with Rhodamine 6G at a wavelength of 566 nm
- Frequency conversion unit frequency-doubled the laser beam to **excite the OH radicals** at a wavelength of **282.9 nm**
- After all correction steps the laser beam has an average energy of 20 mJ/pulse

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Visual investigation of the hydrogen admixture

20 kW burner power, $\lambda=1.0$

- Flame detection with UV probe up to 100% H₂ possible
- Flame stabilizes for all different fuel gas mixtures (0-100% H₂)
- Significant change in flame color and flame shape
- Significant change in the width of the flame base
- Flame height changes slightly with H₂ admixture

OH-PLIF Processing

Post-processing steps are required after the images have been recorded:

- Background subtraction
- Energy correction
- Flat Field correction
- Image reconstruction

OH-PLIF Investigation in the combustion chamber

- Turbulent, nozzle-mixing diffusion flame
- Flame images are an average of 200 individual images at the right side of the figure
- **Local OH concentration equal with increasing hydrogen content**
- **Flame length almost constant**, but flame base wider
- **Due to increased flame turbulence, scattering increases** in the upper region

➤ No critical change in the flame with increasing hydrogen admixture

➤ No design adjustment of the burner nozzle required

Future NO-PLIF measurements in the combustion chamber

Theoretical composites of the exhaust gas

Equilibrium Calculation in Chemkin

High content on water vapor!

- In oxyfuel combustion, the nitrogen content in the oxidizer is eliminated
→ and consequently in the flue gas
- The CO₂ content can be reduced to 0% at pure hydrogen-oxygen flame
- However, the water vapor content in the flue gas increases drastically
- This causes significant difficulties for the analyzers

Last Measurements: Exhaust gas investigation of the hydrogen admixture

Previous measurement: Dry exhaust gas

- **Condensation of the water vapor** in the exhaust gas necessary
- **Dilution of the exhaust gas sample** with nitrogen or carbon dioxide
- **NO_x can be washed out in water**, which leads to deviations from the real wet values
- Errors may also result from adjusting for the dilution factor.
- **Nitrogen oxides increase** slightly with increasing **hydrogen** content

Wet exhaust gas investigation of the hydrogen admixture

- Measuring cell specially designed for high water vapor
- Interference filters evaluate the selective measuring wavelengths at the detector

Components	Measurement range
NO	0-2240 ppm 2240-10000 ppm
NO₂	0-1460 ppm
CO₂	0-30 vol.% 30-100 vol.%
CO	1200-5000 ppm 5000-10000 ppm
H₂O	0-60 vol.% 60-100 vol.%
CH₄	0-1000 ppm 1000-5000 ppm
O₂	0-21 vol.%

Hot-gas multi-analyzer from Endress+Hauser (MCS330P)

Wet exhaust gas investigation of the hydrogen admixture

- **CO₂ concentration decreases** with adding hydrogen
- **O₂ content** in exhaust gas **equal** for all hydrogen admixtures
- **Water vapor increases** with the **hydrogen admixture** to natural gas
- NO_x at the level, only for pure hydrogen-oxygen increases significantly

- **NO_x can not be washed out in water**, which leads to deviations from the real wet values
- No Errors adjusting for the dilution factor

Wet exhaust gas investigation of the hydrogen admixture

- **NO_x concentration** at lower hydrogen admixtures in the same range in all different units
- **NO_x concentration increases** at pure hydrogen-oxygen combustion in all units
- **Trends equal to ppm**

Influence of false air to the exhaust gas

- **Investigations** into the influence of nitrogen on exhaust gas values due to **different oxygen purities**
- Significant increase in nitrogen oxides with increasing nitrogen increase in the oxidizer for all hydrogen admixtures
- Up to 50 vol.-% H₂ only slight increase in nitrogen oxides
- **Significant increase** in nitrogen oxides with increased nitrogen addition **at 100 vol.-% hydrogen admixture**
 - Despite only slightly higher combustion temperatures

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Summary

- Effect of **hydrogen admixture on an oxygen burner**:
 - Flame stabilization
 - Local OH* concentration
 - Wet exhaust gas composites
- Flame length is only slightly reduced in hydrogen operation
- Higher volume flow leads to widening of the flame shape, more turbulence
- Wet analyzer for exhaust gas works for oxyfuel conditions
- High water vapor content can be measured, CO₂ decreases and O₂ equal with increasing hydrogen admixture to natural gas
- Oxidizer quality is crucial for low NO_x values
- **Burner in the 50 kW power level ready for a Retrofit not only in glass industry but also for the material process and steel industry!**

References

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Thank you for your attention!

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